

INFLUENCE OF FAMILY ENVIRONMENT ON PERSONAL SOCIALIZATION

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Abstract: *In this article, personality socialization, personality Information is provided on how important the role of the family is in socialization and what family members should pay more attention to.*

Key words: *Socialization, socialization, personality, development, psychology, pedagogy, society, family, parents, child, community, upbringing.*

Enter

The place of each of us in society, when and under what conditions it appeared, the process of the psychological mechanisms of our integration into society is called *socialization* or *socialization in psychology*.

Socialization is the process by which a person acquires the social norms and cultural values of the society to which he belongs during his life. The goal of socialization is personal characteristics that a child should acquire and social behavior that he should learn. The object of socialization is a person.

A person is a member of a certain society, he is psychologically developed, distinguished from others by his characteristics and behavior.

In order for a person to become a person as a social being, social environment conditions and upbringing are necessary. Under the influence of these, a person develops as a person and becomes a person.

Development is considered a complex process of action, from simple to complex, from bottom to top, from old qualities to new states, renewal, emergence of new, disappearance of old, change in quantity to change in quality.

Literature analysis and methodology

The source of development is the struggle between opposites . The development of the child's personality is based on the philosophical doctrine that a person is a social being. At the same time, a person is a living, biological being. Therefore, the laws of nature's development are also important in its development. Also, as a person is evaluated as a whole being, his development is influenced by biological and social laws together, they cannot be separated from each other. Because age, education, life experience, and other tragic situations and diseases also affect a person's activity and lifestyle.

The process of socialization of a person continues throughout his life, but it is especially intensive during childhood. It is at that time that the foundation of the spiritual development of the individual is created, which increases the importance of the quality of education, increases the responsibility of society, which defines a certain system of coordinates for the educational process, which leads to the formation of a worldview based on universal and spiritual values. includes; development of creative thinking; the ability to strive for new things and find an acceptable solution to life's problems in non-standard situations, to develop high social activity, self-sacrifice, and the ability to work in a team; the need for constant self-education and formation of professional qualities; the ability to make independent decisions develops.

Thus, a person changes throughout his life. He matures both socially and psychologically, and if the upbringing given to the child is appropriate, he matures as a member of society and takes his rightful place in the complex system of social relations. The family plays a key role in a person's

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spiritual qualities, in the emergence of the need and interest in the acquisition of spiritual knowledge. A healthy spiritual and spiritual environment in the family is of inestimable importance for children to grow up mature and mature. Because development is influenced by education. In order to correctly see the qualities of a person and make an accurate assessment, it is necessary to observe him in the course of various relationships. While parents are fulfilling their social duties, they should form love and respect in their children towards those who organize it, make them engage in socially useful work, and follow the rules and social norms while organizing relationships of various kinds. shows a positive role model in all respects in terms of unwavering compliance, creating a healthy lifestyle, ensuring the unity of goals, words and actions in determining the content of their personal lives.

As an integral part of society, the family, which has a socio-psychological basis of influence on the formation of the individual, performs social tasks and also reflects its own characteristics. can create the temperate climate necessary for regeneration. This feeling is one of the unique features of our people's psyche

One of the main goals of the policy carried out in our society today is to raise a mature generation. The 1st President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, IAKarimov, and our government recognize the family as the basis of society, take care of it, and use all the possibilities for its material and household development. For example, our president says about the role and importance of the family in society: "A child lives in a family environment from the day of birth. Family traditions, values, and customs form a child's personality. The most important thing is that children understand and feel the demands of society through the school of family life.

Family is a small group of people based on marriage or consanguinity, common way of life, moral responsibility and mutual support.

The family as a microenvironment has its influence on the mental, physical and social development of the child. Confidence and fear, calmness and anxiety, sincerity and openness in communication or, on the contrary, inaccessibility and coldness - all these qualities are possessed by a person in the family. These qualities are formed before the child goes to school and affect the child's development for a long time. Anxious mothers give rise to anxious children. Because it is in the family that individual abilities, personal, professional interests, and moral standards are formed. The family is responsible not only for laying the foundation of the edifice called man, but also until its last brick is laid. After all, the family factor affects a person throughout his life. From a social point of view, the family is a community in which a person occupies different social statuses. After all, the task of the family is to gradually prepare the child for society. Family helps a person to define himself, to increase his social and creative activity. A parent is an artist, a child is a work of art, and the process of education is art itself. After we gained independence, the restoration of our national values and the national customs and traditions of our people that have been preserved since time immemorial (in addition to the influence of parents, grandparents, relatives, and the neighborhood) are of great importance in this regard. But sometimes, as a result of the weakening of the educational function of the family and the lack of propaganda work, bad habits (drinking, smoking, drug addiction, being influenced by various religious trends, entering the path of spiritual corruption) appear in the behavior of family members. is one of the worrying cases.

Discussion and results

The formation and education of a perfect citizen of society belongs to the level of this

function of the modern family. Because the socialization of the individual takes place in the family first. In order to understand the importance of family - this place, it is enough to analyze the saying "A bird does what it sees in its nest". That is, any child will use the experiences acquired in his family throughout his life and will later teach them to his children. Through upbringing in the family, a certain political-ideological outlook, moral standards and behavior patterns, and physical qualities are inculcated in a person. As a result of the socialization process that takes place in the family, a person learns social norms and values and enters social life. It is in the family that the child learns to work and be independent.

The development of any society depends on a healthy family environment in that society. In a healthy family environment, healthy generations are brought up and grow up. It is known that the socialization of a newborn baby first takes place in the family. It is in this environment that the child adapts to the social environment and learns social norms and values. Based on these, he enters social life. As the child grows up in the family, he always learns from the interactions of the family members. Then social institutions such as kindergarten, school and street enter human life. On this basis, he begins to study and distinguish the behavior and behavior of other people, and learns the methods and forms of communicating with them, and these concepts remain in his adolescence and adulthood. .

The process of social education carried out in the family also takes place in two main directions. On the one hand, the acquisition of social experience occurs in the process of direct interaction of the child with his parents, brothers and sisters. On the other hand, socialization is carried out by observing the characteristics of social interaction of other family members with each other.

Four parameters of parental behavior towards the child were studied: control, maturity requirement, communication, goodwill . **Control:** i.e. trying to influence the child's activities. Determining the level of obedience of the child to the demands of the parents. **Demand for maturity:** Parents pressure children to act at the limits of their mental abilities, at a high social and emotional level. **Communication:** the use of beliefs by parents to gain privileges from the child, to explain his opinion or attitude towards something. **Goodwill:** the extent to which parents show interest in a child, such as praise, joy at his or her successes, warmth, love, care, and affection.

The role of the family is to gradually integrate the child into the society, and his development corresponds to the nature of the person and the culture of the country where he was born. It is the direct duty of parents to teach a child the social task that humanity has accumulated, the culture of the country where he was born and grew up, its moral norms and folk customs.

Every person cannot feel the feeling of the Motherland in the literal sense without understanding the role and functions of the family in the society, and without understanding that the Motherland begins at the threshold. It is in this place that every person first learns the essence of the concepts of "Motherland", "people". Therefore, the family itself is a part of the Motherland. Protection of family honor and concern for its preservation is the basis of socio-political education organized in the family. should be This work is mainly about the traditions of education in every Uzbek family and their improvement, turning national values into an integral part of the lifestyle, harmonizing modern forms of communication culture with eastern forms, labor education, and its important principle of children's happy marriage. can be realized by achieving appreciation as

In order to achieve educational goals in the family, parents use various means of education: they encourage, punish, and try to be an example for the child. Praise given in a friendly manner

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is more effective than praise from indifferent and cold parents. Due to the intelligent use of praise in relation to punishment and prohibition, it is possible to have a positive influence on the formation of a child as a person. Punishment can also be used when the child cannot be changed in any other way. If there is a need for punishment, it is necessary to seek punishment for the behavior as much as possible in order to increase its educational effect. Punishment should be fair, but not too cruel. Punishment that is too severe can cause fear in the child. Punishment will be effective if the child's mistake is explained well. Children who are punished and yelled at more, withdraw from their parents, become emotionally apathetic and show higher aggression.

Conversations held in family settings are particularly noteworthy. Articles on legal topics brought to the public's attention through the mass media, broadcasts, as well as public legal literature and conversations held on the basis of the ideas put forward in them, improve children's legal imagination, perception, literacy, thinking, activism, it leads to determination of greatness, faith and potential. In the family environment, giving children information about their responsibilities and, in turn, showing them ways to exercise their rights can be very effective in this regard. Children's interaction with their parents allows them to practice and improve social skills, which will be very useful later in communication with their peers.

The value and importance of family socialization is that, under its influence, a person is first prepared for a large, independent life, including family life. He develops his own qualities and qualities. Secondly, he will have the opportunity to become a fully mature, mature, intelligent, healthy and healthy person. That is, the family and its healthy spiritual environment enable the child to live in society, to compromise with people similar to him, to work in cooperation, to be professional, to obey the standards of ethics in dealings. educates, prepares psychologically.

Summary

In conclusion, it should be said that a person's future personality, that is, his future life, depends on the level of social well-being of the family, the level of involvement with children in the family. Thus, analyzing the influence of the family in the life of a person, we see that the family is a social institution, the cell of society where the formation of a person comes into life, it is the first house where a person grows up and receives his first life lessons. becomes In the family, a person receives support and help, where he learns to love the world and people, and remembers the kindest and most vivid memories of this throughout his life, warms his heart in the most difficult moments of life and strengthens his bright will. Therefore, the future personality of a person, his future life depends on the level of social well-being of the family, the level of the family's involvement with the child.

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